

Language and Power : A Search for Perspectives with Reference to English as Second Language in India

Russell Al Farabi¹ and Goutam Bandyopadhyay²

¹M.Ed. Student, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira

²Associate Professor, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira

ABSTRACT : The colonial decision to replace Indian languages by English initially as the medium of administrative and legal procedures was to alter the course of our history in decisive ways. Macaulay, in his Minute, was to pronounce a single shelf of European books of greater worth than all the learning in Sanskrit, Persian and Arabic put together. The remarkable thing is that suddenly the eternal value of the Indian classics and antiquity had come to loss all relevance. The continued status of English as the guarantee of upward mobility within a still rigidly stratified society, there has grown to be a segment of the English- knowing middle class which holds the view that English has been 'naturalized' in this country, and hence ought properly to be seen as one of the Indian languages. European values were, naturally, considered somehow inherently better whereas the indigenous culture was often considered somehow barbaric. English was considered as a "road to the light", a tool of "civilization". The Europeans thought that they can bring emancipation to the souls; they considered this as their duty. They sincerely thought they would contribute to the well-being of the native people in the colonies, and their language was elevated into being almost divine. English is often seen as a tool of the Indian Elite-used to widen the gap between the privileged and the underprivileged. These 'Elite' classes see the widespread use of English and its popularity as an urban phenomenon, the result of westernization and an unmistakable form of neo-colonialism. These facts show that in contemporary Indian society some Indians have internalized the history behind the use of English, some even promote the politics such as a colonial history has left behind. In India, there are a great number of sociolinguistic pressures influencing the development of language education. Elitist status of English in India creates problems for the economic development because that means that the education of the mass of people will be ignored. The spread of English throughout India was to be encouraged so that it would become a "genuine link language of the country, not just, as it is at present, the link language of the elite".

Keywords : Power, Colonialism, Discourse, ESL, EFL, Hegemony, Imperialism, English Language Teaching.

The history of English in India is a fascinating story of power and resistance of invasion and absorption, and of authority and subversion; the history is undoubtedly as absorbing as any historical novel. It is also meant to create an awareness and in-depth understanding of the impact of English and English education –their positive as well as negative effects —on the Indian subcontinent. From a symbol of colonialism and imperialism, the English language has become a neutral tool of communication in the new millennium –a global goldmine.

India has been directly and indirectly had influence of the language English on all the fields such as education, science technology etc. Moreover all over India, there is no single language to unite the whole country. Since, in India, several languages are spoken and also one set of people are reluctant to learn one common Indian language, the present generation of educated Indians perceives it and even owns it as their language. It is inseparable from their everyday concerns. Most educated Indians are bilingual. Their emotions, feelings ideas and knowledge are all as much in the English language as in their mother tongue. They cannot put English outside their consciousness as a tool to be used only when needed.

English is often seen as a tool of the Indian Elite-used to widen the gap between the privileged and the underprivileged. These ‘Elite’ classes see the widespread use of English and its popularity as an urban phenomenon, the result of westernization and an unmistakable form of neo-colonialism. These facts show that in contemporary Indian society some Indians have internalized the history behind the use of English, some even promote the politics such as a colonial history has left behind.

The colonial decision to replace Indian languages by English initially as the medium of administrative and legal procedures was to alter the course of our history in decisive ways. Macaulay, in his Minute, was to pronounce a single shelf of European books of greater worth than all the learning in Sanskrit, Persian and Arabic put together. The remarkable thing is that suddenly the eternal value of the Indian classics and antiquity had come to loss all relevance (!). Curzon was to state, “English is the vehicle of learning and of advancement to the small minority; but for the vast bulk it is a foreign tongue which they do not speak and rarely hear.” Gandhiji related English education to Indian slavery – Curzon’s policy was conceived to contain the mischief wrought by English education.

Despite Curzon and Gandhi, however, the historical fact remains that new professional middle class, by virtue of its entrenchment in the administration, in the law courts, in public works and in education, acquired a vested interest in the continuance of English as the official language. Although within Congress itself – there continued to be voices favoring the disbanding of English from public use, the ‘cosmopolitan’ and ‘internationalist’ proclivities of Nehru – militated against the banning of English.

The continued status of English as the guarantee of upward mobility within a still rigidly stratified society, there has grown to be a segment of the English- knowing middle class which holds the view that English has been ‘naturalized’ in this country, and hence ought properly to be seen as one of the Indian languages. On the face of it, this must seem too obviously true; about two to three percent of

Indians do know some English – the problem resides in the refusal or the unwillingness of such opinion to recognize the collusion between English and various system of dominance, both in relation to the Indian political economy and to culture.

Language and Power

Questions about language and power go beyond linguistics into history, sociology, attitude studies, politics and economic considerations. The power of language is intimately connected with societal power. It can be manifested by using persuasion, regulation, inducement or force to add a code to a speech community or by the suppression of a particular language variety and the elevation of another.

This is a fact that English has spread as a result of exploitation and colonization. It is notable that, especially in many ex-colonies of Britain, English is still the language of an exclusive social elite.

Languages can be used to expand the speech community, as a vehicle of cultural or religious enlightenment to deculturize people from their own tradition (to the “civilizing process” also belonged distancing from native cultures: the colonizers wanted to introduce European literature to the natives, at the same time remaining ignorant of their indigenous literatures), to gain economic advantage, to control domains of knowledge and information, and for deception. The following statement by Charles Grant clearly demonstrates the attitudes of the British Raj in India (1831-1832; quoted in Kachru 1986c: 128):

‘The Hindoos err, because they are ignorant and their errors have never fairly been laid before them. The communication

of our light and knowledge to them would prove the best remedy for their disorders.’

The most important reason for the success of English is naturally the historical role of England as a colonial power. In India, for example, the political power naturally attributed a power to the language of the Raj (called the linguistic elitism strategy), and it also became a symbol of political power. English came to be the language of the legal system, higher education, pan-regional administrative network, science and technology, trade and commerce - either because the indigenous languages were not equipped for these roles and English provided for a convenient vocabulary, or because the use of English was considered prestigious and powerful. English became gradually a major tool for acquiring knowledge in the sciences and the humanities. It has come to represent modernization and development, and, as a link language, it has acquired intra-national roles over the years.

Linguistic power can be manifested by using one of the following power strategies: persuasion, regulation, inducement and force. These include linguistic power suppression of a particular language (variety) and the elevation of another. Strategies can include crude linguistic power, indirect psychological pressure and pragmatic power.

Some other reasons for the dominance of English around the world is its propensity for acquiring new identities, its power of assimilation, its adaptability to “decolonization” as a language, its manifestations, and its provision of a flexible medium for literary and other types of creativity across languages and cultures.

The English boom has also induced, what may be called the imitative function- a tendency to imitate the successful English-educated Indian elite, who in turn imitate the 'bold and beautiful' of the West. As a result quite a few people in India have started using English in areas where it is neither necessary nor appropriate. In addition, such people have made code mixed variety a fashionable register, mixing an Indian language with English. In a way, the 'imitative use' and 'code mixing' are producing a language less generation that shows a desire to be successful in life. This mimic generation, one can say, is neither here nor there; they do not have any Indian language as a mother tongue, and they claim that English is their mother tongue. There is nothing derogatory about displacement or the hybrid culture that is being created; maybe they are products of attempts to create new cultures and new languages; may be the 'inner domain' that remained impenetrable during many other linguistic and cultural invasions will get weakened because of the new phenomenon called globalization. Time alone will decide this issue.

Indian English

In India, there are a great number of sociolinguistic pressures influencing the development of language education. Elitist status of English in India creates problems for the economic development because that means that the education of the mass of people will be ignored. The spread of English throughout India was to be encouraged so that it would become a "genuine link language of the country, not just, as it is at present, the link language of the elite".

Under the circumstances, there seems to be an acceptance of Indian English literature as

"one of the voices in which India speaks...it is a new voice, no doubt, but it is as much Indian as the others" (Kachru 1994:528-529). Indian writing represents a new form of Indian culture. It has become assimilated and is today a dynamic element of the culture.

It can be said to be a challenge for the Indian novelist to write about his experiences in a language which has developed in a very different cultural setting; in a "foreign" language; how to create sense of reality and intensity of Indian life in the medium of English language. The integrity of the writers writing in English is often suspect in their own country, and in other English-speaking countries they are treated as marginal to the mainstream of English literature. Indian English writers are sometimes accused of abandoning the national or regional language and writing in a western, "foreign", language.

Stylistic influence from the local languages seems to be a particular feature of much Indian literature in English; the local language structure is reflected as e.g. the literal translation of local idioms. Indian novelists have not only nativized the language in terms of stylistic features; they have also acculturated English in terms of the Indian context.

A view of the mother tongue being the primary medium of literary creativity is still generally held across cultures. Creativity in another tongue is often considered as a deviation from the norm. The native language is considered pure, it is treated as a norm. This causes difficulties for non-native writers of English: it is not rarely that they have to defend themselves writing in English.

The process of nativization is due both to transfer from local language as well as to the

new cultural environment and communicative needs. Because of deep social penetration and the extended range of functions of English in diverse sociolinguistic contexts there are several varieties, localized registers and genres for articulating local social, cultural and religious identities.

Indian English has developed to a more distinctive level than in other countries where English is used as a second language. English in India has evolved characteristic features at the phonological, lexical, syntactic and even at discourse level. Initially, these innovations were rejected by purists, but they are becoming increasingly accepted: English is not anymore treated as a foreign language; it is part of the cultural identity of India. These innovations have led to some problems related to pedagogical standards, national and international intelligibility and typology.

English and Globalization

The process of globalization, facilitated by rapid advancements in information and communications technology and marked by increased mass communication and movement of people, can be viewed as imperialist in spirit. Changes in structural relations have helped maintain global inequalities, which in turn serve the interests of capitalism in English-speaking countries. Thus, English has become the language of capitalism. As well as functioning as the medium of globalisation, English also works as a tool for its extension, the gatekeeper of access to international trade and information.

The attempt to create a dominant global position for English can be traced back to the nineteenth century, when British colonialism reached every continent and language teaching

came to be used for the active development of political unity. English successfully acquired an official status in many countries because it was promoted as a neutral solution to competition between indigenous languages; many African countries have retained it as a *lingua franca* for communication at a national level. Because Britain was one of the earliest countries to develop industrially, English developed a monopoly of certain technical terminology. By the end of the century, the USA became a major influence in the global spread of English, its economy surpassing that of Britain. "The fact that the North Americans speak English" was Bismarck's response in 1898 when asked what he believed was the most important feature in the determining of modern history. Linguistic imperialism was then used in conjunction with military colonisation, with language central to the conduct of trade and the communication of information and cultural norms. Western planning policies, and in particular the introduction of British and American teaching programmes, were instrumental in this process.

Language planning was chiefly justified through the application of the core ideas of Modernisation Theory which argued that countries could be successfully modernised in a similar manner to the rebuilding of Europe. This ethnocentric interventionist approach, which included the Enlightenment ideal of creating human progress through educational investment, produced the perception of a dichotomy between so-called developed and developing countries, whereby the latter needed to be liberated from traditional institutional structures which inhibited economic growth. Furthermore, it was asserted that improvements could be achieved through an imitation of the institutions and cultures of

industrialised countries. Recent approaches, such as Dependency Theory and World Systems Theory, have questioned the notion of a linear development towards modernity and point to the role of aid in disguising business investments.

Modernised western countries are considered responsible for creating and maintaining the barriers to economic prosperity and international equality.

The use of English in maintaining and extending western power has also depended on an imperialist discourse whereby the creation of a hegemonic position for English has been sought.

This has involved the presentation of English language learning as commonsensical; an idea to be internalised even though it may not be in the interests of non-native speakers to do so. English can then be viewed as the ‘Trojan horse’ of western imperialism. The implied superiority of English can be linked to its promotion as a language which is intrinsically varied, interesting and capable of adapting to societal changes although it is, in fact, an extremely difficult language to learn, particularly because of its unusual vowel sounds and highly idiomatic nature. The endeavour to create an ideology whereby acquiring a knowledge of English is necessary to overcome disadvantage is also enhanced through extrinsic factors, with huge levels of resources being allocated towards the training of teachers and the publication of textbooks and dictionaries. Perhaps the most significant aspect relating to the status of English is the emphasis placed on its functional qualities in offering potential access to information, prestige and economic prosperity.

The Role of English in 21st Century—A Search For Alternatives

The onslaught of English can be met if proper planning is done to handle the teaching of English in post independence India. The Great Indian Renaissance can be affected in English and the English language and Western language can be turned to our advantage, if we chisel out anew pattern of education to suit a country like India instead of allowing market conditions to take over education. It is well within the power and purpose of the Indian people to fashion a country of their choice, if English can be used as a servant and not allowed to be the master. Local wisdom can be activated in the search for alternatives; the intuition of the ‘Great Indian People’, their traditions and practices, can be used to get ideas and inspiration in planning an alternative education system.

An educational system, as it is obvious, should meet the aspirations of the people and, at the same time, change society; education must become an instrument of social change and truly educate people. No doubt the systems must produce highly competent professionals- doctors, engineers, managers, teachers, artisans etc.- but, at the same time, it must also train them to critically examine and question, in a creative way, ‘professionalism without social commitment’. This is a dual responsibility the components of which, though they appear to be incompatible, are in fact, complementary. The social component is to make the professionals as conscious as possible of the dangers of professionalism without any social responsibilities. In other words, education must be market-oriented as well as society-oriented. The Consciousness Raising component, which was missing in the colonial plan of education, is

to remove 'illiteracy' among the literates and make them truly educated, contemplative, and thinking citizens. The colonial pattern of education, which was meant to promote and protect the interests of the rulers, was a transplanted model that was implanted in India without taking into account the earlier systems of education that were 'native' in character; the colonial system was not a continuation of the older systems but had different aims and objectives. It was an imported model that conditioned us to live on *received theories* and *received knowledge*.

The decolonized system of education should encourage a critical contemplation of the impact of European education, cultural colonialism, linguistic imperialism and globalization, and expose the imperialistic designs hidden in the imported, alien model. On the one hand, it must encourage a searching scrutiny on our dependence on Euro-centric approaches to education and life, and free the mind from the colonial cussedness that is so very deeply rooted in our thinking, so that the Indian mind can come out of its 'cultural amnesia'. On the other hand, the new system of education must reactivate and reorganize the knowledge systems of the sub continent and make them relevant and beneficial to our present day world; it must enable society to restore destroyed confidence and character so that the deep rooted inferiority complex in Indian school is shed.

The alternatives must strike a balance between romanticizing our past and condemning all that is modern; we don't have to assume that all that is modern is Western and we need not ape the West to be modern. The alternatives we are to think of must make use of modern technology and science, and even colonial

legacies like Western knowledge and the command of English to our advantage. We do not have to walk into the ancient past and try to re-establish a Nalanda or a Takshashila, the ashrams and pathshalas and establish a gurukul type of education. This is not just possible or practical. With the population crossing the one billion mark, an enormous pressure is brought on the resources of the country. Secondly, the present day bureaucracy was not present in the ancient past; there was no University Grants Commissions in those days and universities like Nalanda and Takshila did not have Accounts Officers, Controllers of Examinations, or Registrars. The problem of numbers must be taken into account in our planning and we must strike a balance between the old and the new, and get the best of both. Thus, the interactive discourse in education must take place not only between the East and the West but also between the old and the new within the country. It must also take place among the various linguistic groups, religious communities, and regions and between the urban and the rural people. Only then will the unity in the plurality emerge. Only such a discourse will prevent the hegemony of one over the other. In a land of multiple modules, no one system or layer can be privileged over the other.

Another important task in the new educational system is the bridging of the gap between the languages of India, on the one hand, and English and the English-educated Indians, on the other. A proper, matured dialogue based on the 'yoking' of the cultural and literary productions of the two systems concerned will narrow the communication gap created by the 'colonial divide' and result in productive ploughing of our fertile field. Such yoking will be beneficial

to society at large and create a level field for the non-English-knowing population. English-knowing Indians must be made to realize that English literature is no longer central to our educational or cultural enterprise, and the great literature exists even outside English.

Taken into account all the factors mentioned above, the roles assigned to English in contemporary India need to be reformulated, depending on the needs of the changing conditions. Indians need English but it depends on what they are going to do with it. The changing scenario from *coloniality* to *globality* entails a shift in the aims and objectives of teaching English in India. They can be stated as follows:

1. The market driven utilitarian function :

Taking into account the global market, English must be taught for global communication, career opportunities, and mobility.

2. The welfare driven social function:

We should use English as a source for Indian languages, Indian Knowledge systems, and the lives of the vast majority of people who have been marginalised and exploited so far.

3. The ideology-driven identity projection function:

It means translating and projecting India so that English becomes a window on India’.

In free India, Indians have understood that English is not that the only language for shaping one’s aesthetic sense, cultivating universal humanistic values, cultivating creative and critical thinking, or getting ‘civilized’. All these functions

can be more effectively performed by Indian languages and their literatures with their rich and ancient traditions; they have an age old humanistic tradition and we do not need English for these purposes. English is necessary for mobility, career advancement, opportunities and social and economic purposes. English is the language that opens the door of a global market. As an international language, English has a lot of surrender value throughout the world and learners of English can cash in on that.

Learners of English in India have realized that English is a ‘window to the world’ – an access to the growing fund of knowledge in science and technology. As the Study Group Report says, ‘...with our long tradition in the use of English, we should be able to exploit the richness of this language to the advantage of major Indian languages.’ The English language has the necessary information in every branch of knowledge – agriculture, economics commerce, business, engineering, space technology, bio technology, information technology, consumer products etc.— which is readily available at the click of the mouse over the internet. English is an ‘exploding language’ in a world of ‘information explosion’. We need to profit from the stock of knowledge and information in English. Indians know that we need English for technological purposes and for modernization. That is why English is retained as the language of instruction at Universities.

Indian languages are rich in certain areas like philosophy, religion, literature etc. and English is not going to replace Indian languages in such areas or in the areas of intimacy. English should play a catalytic role or a socially transforming role in contemporary India, and not a literary role as in the days of British Raj. An interface

between English and Indian languages will be to the advantage of the vast majority of non-English-knowing people in India, who, at present, are exploited by the English-knowing minority in the urban areas. Rural India should get the English advantage as well as the technological advantage, which is now available only in 'English India'. Rural India must be empowered with English and the masses must get the advantage. The teaching and learning of English in India should become an agent of social change and social transformation; adapting Macaulay's unutilized 'filtration theory', we must produce a *class of Indians, not only in blood and colour; but also Indian in tastes, in opinion, in morals, and in intellect — a class of Indians who will be socially responsible, productive and committed to the cause of nation-building.*

To achieve these goals, it will be necessary to produce competent people in the art and science of translation. We need to produce not only translated versions of the best of books available in English to help those who are not able to profit from the books in English, but also create original texts in Indian languages, particularly in science, technology, and commerce.

Learners of English in India have realized that English is necessary to talk about their own identity, their languages and literatures, their cultures and values, their land and heritage, their contribution to the commonwealth of knowledge so that the world outside may know what they mean and what they stand for; this 'projection of one's identity' can be done only effectively in an international language like English.

This 'identity-projection' function was effectively activated during the struggle for independence; this function should become one of the important objectives of teaching English in India. This, in a way, reverses one of the roles that English has played so far, that of being a 'window on the world'; we must use English to create a 'window on India'

An 'indigenous approach' based on our own needs and requirements, on our wisdom, suitable to a multi-cultural and multi-lingual context must be evolved for teaching English in India. Decolonizing the colonial English educational pattern in India is also an attempt to examine and study certain fundamental issues like the suitability of Western models as universals, problems in adoption and adaptation, and how adept we are in handling neo-colonialism. Fundamental issues like decolonizing the mind and understanding the power-dynamics are involved in this project. Our attempt in India will be case-study, and this experiment in the process of decolonization could serve as a model for many other areas in the world that are struggling to get rid of exploitation in various forms. Like India's experiment in non-violence that inspired many in the world, our decolonization enterprise can be a source of inspiration to the rest of the colonized world.

No doubt, decolonization enterprise is a massive operation that can be compared with the freedom movement in India. The subcontinent was colonized through education backed by gunpower; the gunpower is gone but the education system is deeply rooted in our country. Colonialism is established in the minds of men and women, and only in the minds of men and women can the foundations of anti-colonialism be built; it is education that can start

the process of decolonization. It can not be done in a day or two; colonialism was built up over a period of time and decolonizing the mind and the system will take time. But someday, somewhere, a beginning must be made –the sooner the better.

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